

The Tonolli Memorial Fund

The Tonolli Fund of SIL was created in 1985 through a bequest from Vittorio and Livia Tonolli, well known limnologists at the Istituto Italiano di Idrobiologia in Pallanza, Italy. The purpose of the fund is to provide assistance to young limnologists in developing countries and encourage them to join SIL. Information about the fund can be found at LIMNOLOGY.ORG/tonolli-memorial-award. Below is a report from a recent Tonolli Fund recipient.

Argentina

Isolation of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in two rivers of Argentina

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Freshwater systems are threatened by overpopulation, polluted runoff and global warming, resulting in increased nutrient and pollutant inputs (Carbone *et al.*, 2013). This promotes the occurrence of pathogenic microorganisms, inducing the overall deterioration of water quality. In particular, *Escherichia coli* can be detected in elevated densities in human and animal feces, sewage, and waters receiving fecal pollution. *Escherichia coli*'s presence in water indicates the possible existence of fecal pathogens and, consequently, a potential risk to human health (Ishii & Sadowsky, 2008). Some strains of *E. coli* have evolved into highly versatile and frequently deadly pathogens for humans (Barbau-Piednoir *et al.*, 2018), such as Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC). Its pathogenicity is related to the production of the Shiga toxin, encoded by the *stx1* and *stx2* genes (*e.g.* Clements *et al.*, 2012). STEC is responsible for Hemolytic Uremic Syndrome, which is endemic in Argentina, with the highest rate of pediatric cases worldwide (Rivas *et al.*, 2014). Other types of diarrheagenic *E. coli* (DEC), including enteropathogenic (EPEC), enterotoxigenic (ETEC), enteroinvasive (EIEC) and enteroaggregative (EAEC) *E. coli*, are harmful to humans, and each is encoded by different genes (Table 1). These categories can cause different degrees of diarrheal diseases in humans depending on the virulence factors involved. Recent studies have shown that the *E. coli* genome has a high plasticity allowing it to adapt to new niches and survive in stressful conditions, (Tanaro *et al.*, 2018) and to evolve into new hybrid strains as new pathotypes (Nyholm, 2016).

Fig. 1: A. Site 2 of Rojas River. B. Site 3 of Salado River.

Fig. 2: Map depicting the rivers selected for this study. A. Selected sites of the Rojas River surrounding Rojas City. B. Selected sites of the Salado River surrounding Junín City. Yellow arrows indicate the direction in which the river flows. S2 in Rojas River and S3 in Salado River (red circle) indicate the location of the wastewater treatment plant. Black arrows indicate the type of DEC found in each site and, between parentheses, the number of each one. S1: site 1, S2: site 2, S3: site 3, S4: site 4. STEC: Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*, EAEC: enteroaggregative *E. coli*, EPEC: enteropathogenic *E. coli*, EAEC-It-st: enteroaggregative *E. coli* with *It* and *st* genes.

Table 1. Diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* and genes that encode each pathotype. STEC: Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*, EAEC: enteroaggregative *E. coli*, EPEC: enteropathogenic *E. coli*, ETEC: enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, EIEC: enteroinvasive *E. coli*

Diarrheagenic <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Genes
STEC	<i>stx1/stx2/rfbO157</i>
EAEC	<i>aggR/aaIC</i>
EPEC	<i>eae</i>
ETEC	<i>lt/st</i>
EIEC	<i>lpah</i>

The Pampean Region (Argentina) is home to thousands of aquatic systems including rivers, streams and shallow lakes, which are surrounded by agricultural and livestock activities and urban impacts (Quirós *et al.*, 2002). The Salado and Rojas Rivers, located in this region, are impacted by anthropogenic activities since they are located near cities (Junín and Rojas, Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina, respectively) (Fig. 1). We selected four sites in each river based on their proximity to cities: Site 1 (S1) was located upstream of the city, site 2 (S2) and site 3 (S3) near the city, and site 4 (S4) downstream of the city (Fig. 2). We collected samples during March, June, September and December of 2021 and obtained samples suspected of fecal/*E. coli* contamination. The aim of this study was to identify and characterize the *E. coli* strains by detecting specific genes (Table 1) encoding for different virulence factors using multiplex PCR. These genes correspond to different diarrheagenic *E. coli*

strains: STEC, EAEC, EPEC, EIEC and ETEC. A total of eleven pathogenic *E. coli* strains were detected, three isolated from the Rojas River (1 STEC-*stx1/stx2* and 2 EAEC) and eight from the Salado River (1 STEC-*stx2*, 3 EPEC, 3 EAEC and 1 EAEC (*aaIC-st-lt*), as shown in Fig. 2.

The presence of these pathogenic *E. coli* in most of the selected sites in both rivers indicates that anthropogenic activities along the river banks affect the bacterial composition of the water, representing a public health risk. Further studies are needed to elucidate the origin of these bacteria and their survival time in the river. However, the detection of these DEC, together with the abundance of total and thermotolerant coliforms, *E. coli* and environmental data, can provide new basic knowledge about the effect of human activities on the water quality and health of Pampean rivers. Furthermore, the insights gained in this study can provide scientists, policymakers and managers more effective models for the protection, management and restoration of aquatic sites.

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Rojas River, Buenos Aires, Argentina. Photo by Guillermina Nuozzi.